

Maria's Literary Journey through Tere Liye's Books

Kurniawan Arif Maspul

University of the People, Pasadena CA
kurniawanarifmaspul@my.uopeople.edu

Abstract

This portfolio addresses the remarkable impact of Tere Liye's book series on the cognitive, emotional, and social development of an 11-year-old reader during three months. Maria's interaction with the series is examined using Piaget's cognitive development theory and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, revealing considerable advances in abstract thinking and empathy abilities. The portfolio paper emphasizes the importance of parental participation and a rich reading environment in instilling a lifetime love of literature and learning, demonstrating literature's transforming power on young minds.

Keywords: Metacognition, Socioemotional Development, Neuroplasticity, Multiliteracies, Holistic Pedagogy

Maria, my 11-year-old daughter, has been on a fascinating reading trip for the past three months, immersed in Tere Liye's engaging book series. Maria's reading voyage through Tere Liye's book series from January to March 2024 encompasses a wide range of themes, characters, and narratives, each of which contributes to her cognitive, emotional, and social growth. The following are the titles of the books:

1. Bumi
2. Bulan
3. Matahari
4. Bintang
5. Ceros & Batozar
6. Komet
7. Komet Minor
8. Selena
9. Nebula
10. Siputih
11. Lumpu
12. Bibi Gill
13. Sagaras
14. Matahari Minor
15. ILY

Tere Liye, a well-known Indonesian novelist, has created a riveting series of stories that transport readers to fascinating realms (Liye, 2024). Each book in the series, with titles such as

"Bumi," "Bulan," "Matahari," "Bintang," and "Ceros & Batozar," provides a new and captivating adventure. In "Bumi," readers are engaged in a vividly imagined universe, solving puzzles and meeting unique people. "Bulan" transports us to the moon, where secrets and wonders await. "Matahari" sheds light on a brilliant world brimming with astounding beauty and profound insights.

The series continues in "Bintang," in which readers embark on a heavenly adventure, exploring the depths of the universe. "Ceros & Batozar" exposes us to a dynamic duo that embark on adventurous missions and face remarkable challenges. As the book progresses, "Komet" takes readers on a cosmic journey, while "Komet Minor" reveals secret dimensions and surprising turns. "Selena" delves into the heart of a captivating character's existence, revealing her complexities and wants. "Nebula" depicts a celestial vision, whilst "Siputih" transports readers to an enticing world of magic and wonder. "Lumpu" reveals a road of self-discovery and personal development.

"Bibi Gill" tells the compelling narrative of an extraordinary woman, whilst "Sagaras" transports readers to a realm of fantastic animals and old traditions. "Matahari Minor" reveals a tiny but equally enchanting celestial body with its own stories and mysteries. Finally, "ILY" tells a moving and emotional story about the depths of love, relationships, and life's complications. The Tere Liye book series transports readers on an incredible literary trip where imagination knows no limitations and the power of narrative shines brightly. Each book provides a one-of-a-kind storytelling experience, enthraling readers with different topics, distinctive characters, and captivating plots.

Cognitive Developments and Other Implications

Maria's passionate reading of Tere Liye's novels is consistent with Piaget's theory of cognitive development, namely the concrete operational stage. According to Piaget (2013), children aged 7 to 11 begin to demonstrate more complex logical thinking and grasp of abstract concepts. Maria's investigation of complicated tales, character motivations, and moral quandaries in Tere Liye's works reflects her cognitive development as she grapples with abstract concepts and opposing viewpoints.

In contrast, Vygotsky's sociocultural theory emphasizes the importance of social interactions and cultural experiences in influencing children's cognitive and emotional development (Vygotsky & Cole, 1978). Maria has been exposed to a wide range of emotions and viewpoints thanks to Tere Liye's rich narrative and various characters, which has honed her ability to comprehend and empathize with the experiences of others. Maria's involvement with the emotional depth of the characters and the moral intricacies of the stories improves her emotional intelligence and empathy abilities, which are essential for navigating social interactions and understanding human behavior.

Moreover, Maria's immersion in Tere Liye's literary universe not only improves her reading comprehension and vocabulary, but it also instills a lifetime passion for reading and learning. Research has indicated that early exposure to literature and literacy-rich environments builds the groundwork for academic performance and lifelong learning (Bus *et al.*, 1995; Maspul, 2024). Maria is honing her critical thinking abilities, broadening her worldview, and cultivating a love of literature that will last her a lifetime.

Parenting Wisdom in Cultivating Early Literacy

Parenting is an art that comprises cultivating a child's love of books, which is essential for their cognitive growth. In this quest, knowledge from developmental psychology and empirical research can help parents create a rich reading environment that promotes intellectual growth beginning in infancy. Parents are urged to engage their children in the realm of reading and stories from the time they are born. Even if newborns do not understand the meaning of words, exposure to language patterns and narratives lays the neurological foundation for future language acquisition and comprehension (Dehaene-Lambertz *et al.*, 2006; Maspul, 2022).

In order to foster a child's love of literature, reading experiences must be fun and exciting. Parents can turn reading sessions into exciting experiences that capture young minds and develop a good link with literacy by introducing storytelling into daily routines and adopting expressive voices and interactive features (Bus *et al.*, 1995). As influential role models, parents have a huge influence on their children's views about reading. Genuine excitement for books and reading materials is an effective motivation for children to replicate. When children observe their parents' love of literature, they are more likely to develop a comparable enthusiasm and interest about the world of books (Bus *et al.*, 1995).

Establishing a dedicated reading environment in the home emphasizes the value of literacy. Parents can show their children that reading is cherished and prioritized in the home by providing a pleasant reading nook complete with comfy seats and an assortment of age-appropriate books. This designated place provides a safe haven for literary exploration while also instilling a love of books and storytelling. Allowing children to make individual choices when picking reading materials promotes autonomy and intrinsic drive. Offering a varied range of books across genres and topics encourages youngsters to explore their interests and preferences, instilling a sense of control over their reading journey. Allowing adolescents to choose their own reading materials fosters a lifetime love of books based on personal satisfaction and curiosity (Bergin & Bergin, 2011).

Recognizing and praising children's literacy development progress and achievements is critical for building confidence and self-esteem. Recognizing children's efforts, whether they are learning a new word, finishing a book, or sharing their ideas on a tale, creates a sense of pride and success. This positive reinforcement strengthens children's confidence in their talents and motivates them to keep exploring and developing their literary skills (Bergin & Bergin, 2011). Engaging children in meaningful conversations about the books they read encourages critical thinking and comprehension. Parents promote a culture of debate and intellectual curiosity by encouraging their children to communicate their ideas, opinions, and interpretations. Dialogic reading not only improves children's comprehension of the text, but it also develops their analytical skills and encourages them to think critically about their surroundings (Wasik & Bond, 2001).

Access to a diverse range of reading resources is critical for broadening children's literary horizons and encouraging their curiosity. Providing children with a variety of reading materials, ranging from traditional print books to e-books, audiobooks, and digital platforms, stimulates discovery and exposes them to new genres, authors, and perspectives. Parents may help their

children become well-rounded readers with a comprehensive view of the world by providing them with a diverse range of reading experiences (Bergin & Bergin, 2011).

Integrating literacy into daily routines emphasizes the value of reading as an essential component of life. Whether it's reading aloud at mealtimes, telling bedtime stories before going to bed, or doing literacy-themed activities during playtime, including literacy into everyday activities makes learning more natural and pleasant for kids. This seamless integration of literacy promotes accidental learning and maintains the idea that reading is a lifetime goal to be treasured and embraced rather than a skill to be mastered (Wasik & Bond, 2001).

Parenting wisdom consists in cultivating a child's love of literature and providing them with the tools, resources, and support they require to embark on a lifelong path of literacy inquiry and discovery. Parents have an important role in influencing their children's cognitive development and preparing them for a future full of limitless possibilities by creating a rich literary environment, engaging them in meaningful discourse, and recognizing their accomplishments.

Conclusion

Maria's three-month immersion in Tere Liye's book series has fueled her imagination with intriguing experiences while simultaneously acting as a catalyst for her cognitive, emotional, and social development. Maria's engagement with complex narratives and different characters, which aligns with Piaget's concrete operational stage and Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, has deepened her comprehension of abstract concepts and polished her empathy. Her newfound love of literature, encouraged by early exposure and parental support, lays the framework for a lifetime of intellectual curiosity and personal development. Maria's literary discovery, which includes the creation of a rich reading environment and significant parental involvement, demonstrates the deep power of literature on shaping young minds and developing lifelong learners.

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